

D8.5 ELOQUENCE DMP 2

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Abstract	This deliverable represents the second iteration of the ELOQUENCE Data Management Plan (DMP). It provides information on how the consortium partners handle research information following the FAIR principle and thus fulfill their obligation to satisfy relevant ethics and legal rules. The input of each project partner concerning their responsibilities for data management is included to ensure a comprehensive approach to data management throughout the project.		

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable. Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This document sets out the protocols used by the project partners for handling data processing during project implementation and after the project has been completed. It contains a Data Management Plan (DMP) that covers the necessary aspects for proper data processing. The DMP contains details about the life cycle of the project data, including data processing activities and protection measures. It covers the collection, storage, access, sharing, protection, retention and destruction of data, including personal data. It also presents the main regulatory data protection principles and standards that each partner must comply with when carrying out project activities. Each project partner responsible for handling the data collected, stored, or used in the project has contributed comprehensive information on data management, which is included in this document. As it is the second iteration of the DMP, the deliverable provides additional inputs and updates from partners regarding their data management activities arising out of the project's progress.

2 Introduction

Innovative research projects such as ELOQUENCE involve extensive data processing that often includes sensitive information. Compliance with legal and ethical standards, including the development of a Data Management Plan (DMP), is essential. This DMP outlines the generation, openness, use, and storage of data and emphasizes "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" approach to ensure sound data governance and maintain the integrity of the research. Beyond regulatory compliance, effective data management ensures high-quality, accessible, and well-organized data that promotes efficient research practices and facilitates study replication and validation.

The DMP delineates data handling procedures and key features during and after the project and serves as an iterative document that evolves as the project progresses. It provides an overview of the datasets, sets out rules for data handling and emphasizes the importance of data management in promoting excellence in research and facilitating data sharing for future projects.

This is the second iteration of the DMP and provides further details on data management. It includes input from the project partners and provides insightful details on data-handling practices related to the project.

2.1 Purpose and Scope

The DMP for the ELOQUENCE project covers the entire lifecycle of the research data, from planning to publication and beyond. It describes the steps, including research design, data collection, processing and analysis, publication and sharing, data preservation and reuse. By adhering to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and rules outlined in the DMP, the project ensures compliance with data processing and privacy requirements while effectively managing data generation, use, access, curation, and storage. This DMP is the second edition and contains more detail than its predecessor, which was successfully submitted in June 2024 (M6). The DMP is the living document and the third iteration will be submitted in the end of the project (M36).

2.2 Relation to other work packages, deliverables, and activities

The DMP is considered a valuable source for the regulation of data processing and data protection. Therefore, this deliverable should be considered not only as a complementary but also as an additional source of regulation for this project. The DMP is transversal and concerns the processing of data and personal data in all work packages and research activities of the project. It sets out the specific measures that allow for adequate processing and protection of data. Therefore, the application of the DMP should be prevalent in all project activities where data is processed.

Considering that different categories of data are processed in the context of research, the DMP is crucial for the proper implementation of the legal and ethical requirements and its relevant deliverables (Deliverables 8.2 and 8.3 "Ethics Compliance Management Reports"), as well as the Deliverable 9.1 (OEI – Requirement No 1). It is also crucial for the proper performance of the project pilots. Also, the DMP complements the project management and the associated WP8. In addition, all dissemination activities must take into account the rules and principles of the DMP when publishing certain datasets. All activities related to the development of any methodology, tools, and technologies used for data processing must be based on the principles set out in this DMP.

2.3 Structure of the deliverable

This DMP consists of six chapters. The introduction is followed by a presentation of FAIR principles from a conceptual point of view. Chapter 3 on the FAIR principles, provides only an overview as the first iteration of the DMP addressed the question of which principles should be implemented in order to obtain Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable data. The following Chapter 4 outlines the DMP governance within this project, while Chapter 5 provides an overview of the security strategies and tactics used to secure the data within the project implementation. Finally, Chapter 6 summarizes the data governance mechanism implemented in the ELOQUENCE and provides the description of the updates in data management activities from the relevant partners. At the very end, this DMP is rounded off with brief conclusions.

Annex 8.1 of this document contains the DMP Questionnaire that project partners that process data within this project have answered, whereas Annex 8.2 includes an overview of the datasets that are collected/created within this project.

3 FAIR principles

The FAIR principles, as set out in the EC guidelines, serve as the cornerstone for effective research data management in today's world of exponential growth in data volume and complexity. These principles — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable — have been developed to address the challenges associated with managing vast amounts of data while ensuring its usability and integrity across different research domains.

- **Findable data:** Enhancing data discoverability is essential for its effective utilization. ELOQUENCE partners are responsible for boosting data discoverability by developing metadata and strong identification systems. This guarantees that valuable research findings are readily discoverable and accessible to relevant stakeholders. Public data, meant for broader distribution, is easily accessible through designated communication channels, promoting transparency and knowledge sharing. On the other hand, confidential data, which is subject to stringent access restrictions, is safeguarded and made available exclusively to authorized entities, all while adhering to data protection regulations.
- **Data Accessibility:** Access to project data is influenced by various factors, such as the data type, technical security measures, and organizational protocols. Partners are responsible for defining access rights based on these factors, ensuring a balance between facilitating data access and preserving the confidentiality and integrity of the data. While some datasets are meant for public sharing to encourage collaboration and innovation, others may need restricted access to safeguard sensitive information. The Grant Agreement (GA) provides a framework for defining access rights and ensures adherence to contractual obligations and legal requirements.
- **Interoperable Data:** Interoperability is key to enabling smooth data sharing and integration within the research ecosystem. To support this, data generated under the ELOQUENCE is stored in standardized formats and protocols, ensuring compatibility across various systems and platforms. By adhering to widely accepted standards (as specified in section B3 of the questionnaire (Annex 8.1) and using compatible software solutions, the partners ensure that research data remains adaptable and can be seamlessly integrated with external datasets. This interoperability fosters collaborative synergy and allows researchers to derive actionable insights from diverse data sources.
- **Reusable Data:** The concept of data reuse highlights the sustainable application of research outcomes as a driver for further scientific exploration and innovation. Partners are dedicated to making project-generated data accessible for reuse, ensuring that intellectual property rights and ethical standards are upheld. Proper referencing and permissions are managed to support the ethical and legal reuse of data, fostering a culture of transparency and scientific integrity. Deliverables designated for public dissemination are made available through project websites and institutional repositories (for example, the project partners use [GitHub](#) for the code availability and [Zenodo](#) – for datasets), enabling broader distribution while safeguarding attribution and usage rights.

In essence, adherence to the FAIR principles embodies a commitment to sound data management and promotes a culture of transparency, collaboration, and innovation within ELOQUENCE. By adhering to these principles, project partners ensure that research data remains a valuable and accessible resource that promotes scientific progress and societal impact. In addition, continued compliance with the provisions of the GA relating to intellectual property rights and project ownership ensures the accountability and integrity of data management practices, safeguarding the interests of all stakeholders involved.

Further details on the relevant contractual obligations related to the FAIR principles, as outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA), are provided in the first iteration of the Data Management Plan (DMP), presented as deliverable D8.4. Additionally, explanations of the ethics requirements and the actions/measures decided at the project consortium level are included in the ethics deliverables (Deliverable 8.2 and Deliverable 8.3: Ethics Compliance Management Reports). These actions/measures are essential for the proper implementation of the FAIR principles. Moreover, specific steps taken by the project partners to comply with the FAIR principles are detailed in the partners' responses, which can be found in Annex 8.2 of this document.

4 Data protection and DMP

Ensuring proper data protection, including the lawful handling of personal data, is central to the successful implementation of a Data Management Plan (DMP). The first version of the DMP submitted in M6 outlined the privacy governance mechanism. All project partners are fully informed of the legal and ethical obligations related to personal data protection. They have diligently followed the prescribed guidelines and measures to safeguard the data and ensure that the DMP aligns with the agreed-upon plans.

Data protection is not limited to the implementation of the DMP, but also relates to the fulfillment of the ethics and legal requirements within the ELOQUENCE project. Considering this, the relevant deliverables (Deliverable 9.1 (OEI – Ethics Requirement 1) and Deliverable 8.2 (Ethics Compliance Management Report I) provide a comprehensive framework of applicable data protection requirements and the scope of measures for their fulfillment integrated in the ELOQUENCE project. For example, the data protection requirements regarding the procedures for involvement of external stakeholders and research participants in the ELOQUENCE project are scrutinized in Deliverable 9.1. It determined the privacy governance mechanism by specifying how the partners in the ELOQUENCE consortium facilitate privacy-by-design approach, adhere to data protection principles, assess and mitigate risks concerning processing of personal data, ensure data security and provide clear allocation of roles and responsibilities thus facilitating strong accountability in processing of personal data. Deliverable 8.2 further detailed the data protection risks that can arise out of the project's activities (such as the inadequate informed consent, privacy breaches and data security, misuse of personal data in dissemination activities) and the measures taken by partners to mitigate them.

The project partners have collectively put in place technical and organizational measures to prevent unauthorized data use or disclosure, including protection against the mosaic effect¹, where identification can occur by combining data from different sources. These protective measures encompass encryption and access controls through secure logins, collection of only the data which is strictly necessary, use of pseudonymization/anonymization techniques, the installation of regularly updated security software on devices, and the execution of routine data backups.

In order to comply with the requirement to take security measures to prevent unauthorized access to personal data or processing equipment, the project partners have undertaken to comply with the minimum threshold for ensuring data security. They implement appropriate technical and organizational measures that comply with the relevant provisions of the GDPR. When assessing the appropriateness of these measures, considerations such as the state of the art, the implementation costs in relation to the risks and the type of personal data to be protected are taken into account (more about data security in the following chapter).

¹ <https://iapp.org/news/a/beyond-gdpr-unauthorized-reidentification-and-the-mosaic-effect-in-the-eu-ai-act>

5 Data Security

ELOQUENCE is a research project conducted by a consortium of multiple project partners. While there is no single data security standard that all partners must adhere to, every partner is obligated to implement information security management practices to ensure the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of data. These practices consist of various components, each designed to ensure that the project complies with the highest security and regulatory standards.

To begin with, partners are encouraged to develop comprehensive information security policies that outline the overall security strategy, guidelines, and technical requirements. These policies should be shared with all project stakeholders to ensure a unified understanding of security protocols. To enhance the security framework, partners should incorporate information security efforts into a well-structured management system. This includes clearly defining and assigning roles and responsibilities for information security within specific teams. Risk management processes should be in place to identify, assess, and mitigate potential security threats. It is also essential that all project team members are thoroughly informed about security protocols and their responsibilities concerning information security.

When managing project resources, including any data collected or created, it is critical to ensure that resources are properly classified and assigned to responsible owners. This guarantees that assets, such as data, are afforded the appropriate level of protection throughout their lifecycle. Access control must be strictly enforced, with permissions granted only when necessary and revoked immediately after use. Regular security audits should be conducted to assess the effectiveness of these access control measures.

Cryptography plays a vital role in safeguarding sensitive data. Based on current recommendations and risk assessments, appropriate cryptographic techniques should be employed to ensure data integrity and confidentiality. Additionally, physical and environmental security measures should be put in place to prevent unauthorized access to premises and assets. These security measures must be designed to protect both the research process and the data being handled by project partners. As such, security should be managed by dedicated teams that actively monitor security incidents and take swift action when required. In the event of a security breach, there must be a clearly defined and enforced incident management process.

Lastly, all project partners are fully committed to complying with relevant regulations and standards. They will ensure that the research activities and project operations adhere to applicable regulations, minimizing the risk of non-compliance and fostering trust in the project.

The data security approach outlined here takes a strategic and tactical approach, adhering to the highest security standards. However, the specific security measures are detailed in the partners' responses (available in Annex 8.2).

6 DMP Governance

6.1 Outline of Data Governance in ELOQUENCE

As outlined in the first iteration of the DMP, data governance in the ELOQUENCE project is the ongoing process that started before the launch of project activities. In accordance with the Ethics Appraisal Schema,² an additional work package (WP9) was set up to deal with the ethics requirements and the deliverable 9.1 was submitted, as described in Chapter 4 herein. At the same time, the tasks related to legal and ethics compliance are included in WP8 and are closely related to WP9. Nevertheless, all WPs should pay attention to legal and ethical requirements as well as security and confidentiality management.

The development of the first iteration of the DPM (submitted in M6) started with the development of the questionnaire to collect the required information on data processing and data management. The questionnaire was distributed to all project partners and they were familiarized with the questionnaire during the workshop. All project partners contributed to the development of the DMP by entering information about the data they collected in the questionnaire. By completing the questionnaire, they provided details of their own data processing activities.

The DMP questionnaire (Annex 8.1) is a comprehensive tool designed to gather relevant information for the development of the current and future iterations of the Data Management Plan (DMP). It consists of five sections, each focusing on different aspects of data management. Section A collects details about the data collection or generation process, including data types, formats, origins, and methods used to ensure privacy and manage data effectively. Section B focuses on aligning data management practices with the FAIR principles, examining aspects like data discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse. Section C ensures compliance with GDPR by addressing the processing of personal data, including its types, purposes, and adherence to data protection principles. Section D collects information about data storage, retention, and deletion procedures to assess security, compliance, and risks. Lastly, Section E allows for the inclusion of additional national, funder, or sector-specific data management procedures. Overall, the questionnaire promotes transparency, accountability, and ethical data practices within the project.

6.2 Updates from the partners regarding data governance

For this second iteration of the DMP, the DMP questionnaire provides the mechanism to collect the updates from the partners regarding their data processing and governance activities. As the first version of the DMP provided a rather comprehensive vision of the data governance in ELOQUENCE and this second iteration is delivered one year after the first DMP, the scope of updates from partners is not extensive. In particular, most of the project's partners declared the absence of updates regarding their data governance activities. At the same time, three partners (UNS, TL and OM) informed on the additional information on data governance they gained through the progress in the project's activities. These updates concern:

- the discovery of metadata standards applicable in the relevant discipline of data processing (OM; UNS; TID);
- change of data types and formats (TL; TID);
- internal security procedures for data storing and processing (TID);
- clarifications on the procedures of making data accessible and of the relevant restrictions (UNS);
- clarification on the aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods applicable to the data (UNS).

These updates, while not reshaping the data governance mechanisms of the relevant partners and the whole ELOQUENCE project, increase the maturity of the data management procedures and adherence to the FAIR principles by making data more accessible, findable, interoperable, and reusable. The detailed updated responses of the relevant partners (UNS, TID, TL and OM), as well as the previously provided responses of the partners that declared no updates are provided in the Annex 8.2 of the deliverable.

² HE Regulation 2021/695: Eligible actions and ethical principles (Article 18) and Ethics (Article 19); HE Programme Guide as of May 15, 2025 (v 5.0).

7 Conclusion

The second iteration of the ELOQUENCE Data Management Plan (DMP) reflects the project's continued commitment to responsible, ethical, and legally compliant data management. Building upon the foundations established in the initial DMP (M6), this version consolidates updated contributions from project partners and integrates improvements driven by evolving project needs and increased maturity in data governance practices.

The DMP ensures that all data processing within the ELOQUENCE project adheres to the FAIR principles—making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—while respecting the balance between openness and the protection of sensitive or personal information. Through comprehensive measures addressing data protection, security, and governance, the DMP provides a reliable framework for data lifecycle management across all work packages.

While most partners reported no substantial changes in their data management practices since the first iteration, updates from several contributors indicate progress in metadata standardization, data retention, security and access protocols, and anonymization techniques. These refinements demonstrate the consortium's adaptability and ongoing efforts to uphold high standards in data stewardship.

The DMP will continue to evolve in response to the project's developments, with a final iteration planned at the project's conclusion. As such, it remains a dynamic and integral document, ensuring that the ELOQUENCE consortium meets both regulatory obligations and the scientific community's expectations for data transparency, integrity, and reusability.

8 Annex

Annexes contain the template of the DMP questionnaire as well as the answers provided by the project partners.

8.1 DMP Questionnaire

DMP Questionnaire

This questionnaire should provide details necessary for the development of the Data Management Plan. The Data Management Plans (DMPs) is a key element of good data management. The DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by ELOQUENCE project.

The methodology for the development of the DMP is based on the European Commission [Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020](#) and the best practices regarding personal data protection.

General Information		
Partner Name		
Corresponding person (email)		
Name of the dataset		
A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? ³	<i>Please Specify</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect? ⁴	<i>Please Specify</i>
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect? ⁵	<i>Please Specify</i>
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how? ⁶	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
5	What is the origin of the data? ⁷	<i>Please Specify</i>
6	What is the expected size of the data? ⁸	<i>Please Specify</i>
7	To whom might the data be useful? ⁹	<i>Please Specify</i>
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data? ¹⁰	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):

³ State the purpose of the data collection/generation.

⁴ Define the nature of the data, e.g. quantitative, qualitative, numeric, text, audio, structured, unstructured, etc.

⁵ Define the format of the data, e.g. txt, xlsx, doc, pdf, etc.

⁶ Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any).

⁷ Specify the origin of the data.

⁸ State the expected size of the data (if known).

⁹ Outline the data utility, to whom will it be useful, e.g. research groups, private sector, citizens, etc.

¹⁰ Define if privacy preservation techniques are required before making your data open.

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data			
B1 - Making data Findable			
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
2	What metadata will be created?	Please Specify	
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline? ¹¹	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):	
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	Please Specify	
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use? ¹²	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
B2 - Making data openly accessible			
1	Accessibility ¹³	<input type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data	
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why ¹⁴	Please Specify	
3	How will the data be made accessible ¹⁵	Please Specify	
4	Which repository will be used? ¹⁶	Please Specify	
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Please Specify	
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):	
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? ¹⁷	Please Specify	
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Please Specify	
10	Is there a need for a data access committee? ¹⁸	Please Specify	
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	Please Specify	
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Please Specify	
B3 - Making data interoperable			
1	File format		
	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM Other (please specify):

¹¹ Define the metadata standards you use. Link regarding the metadata standards: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards/list>.

¹² Outline the approach towards search keyword (e.g. search keywords will be provided when the dataset will be uploaded to the repository).

¹³ Will data produced and/or used in the project be made openly available?

¹⁴ If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

¹⁵ Specify how the data will be made available, e.g. by deposition in a repository.

¹⁶ Specify which repository will you use, e.g. Zenodo, open-access journal, project website, etc.

¹⁷ E.g. Zenodo, open-access journal, project website, etc.

¹⁸ Specify why.

	<input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	<input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	<input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	<i>Please Specify</i>		
B4 - Increase data re-use				
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?¹⁹	<i>Please Specify</i>		
2	Data owner²⁰	<i>Please Specify</i>		
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?²¹	<i>Please Specify</i>		
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?²²	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):		
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?²³	<i>Please Specify</i>		
C - Personal Data				
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions				
1	What types of personal data will you process?²⁴	<i>Please Specify</i>		
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?²⁵	<i>Please Specify</i>		
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	<i>Please Specify</i>		
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?²⁶	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No		
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?²⁷	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No		
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No		
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No		
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Please Specify</i>		

¹⁹ License conditions: Copyright, Creative Commons, Open License, etc. A list of licenses can be found here <https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>

²⁰ List the data owner, the copyright owner, the intellectual property owner.

²¹ E.g. Immediately, after the end of the project (specify the exact time), along with the publication of main results, etc. If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

²² If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

²³ Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable, e.g. 5 years after the conclusion of the project.

²⁴ E.g. email addresses, phone numbers, affiliation, position, research notes, interviews

²⁵ E.g. for contacting project partners, for conduct interviews necessary for research purposes

²⁶ Special categories of data are personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation

²⁷ If yes, you should collect evidence that previous beneficiary has lawfully processed the data and applied appropriate technical and organizational measures for securing data.

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	<i>Please Specify</i>
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data) ²⁸	<i>Please Specify</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	<i>Please Specify</i>
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<i>Please Specify</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? ²⁹	<i>Please Specify</i>

²⁸ Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.

²⁹ Indicate if you must adhere to other policies and procedures for data management.

8.2 Project partners answers

i. TID

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? ³⁰	Recording of unstructured/structured voice dialogs in a smart-home environment. Simulated situations where, e.g., actors act like friends/family and play Trivia game while keep a conversation on family/work affairs in a living room. The purpose is to create a benchmark dataset.
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	Audio data
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	mp3/wav files / automatic transcriptions / intent and slot annotations
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
5	What is the origin of the data?	Recordings performed by TID employees that perform, like actors, several common situations in a home
6	What is the expected size of the data?	4-5 sessions of 1-2 hours
7	To whom might the data be useful?	WP1 for metrics and benchmark, WP2 for grounding LLMs, WP5 for development of pilot number 1
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): simulated names/addresses or familiar/friend relationships given as scripting to actors
B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	Speech, Transcriptions. Slot and intent annotations and summaries of the conversations
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): ctm format for transcriptions, IOB tagging format for slots, wav files for speech <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	Please Specify
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	The intention is to share the dataset with the consortium and with research community but depending on TID policy and upon agreement from our legal department
3	How will the data be made accessible	Under EULA agreement for research purpose
4	Which repository will be used?	Internal TID. In case we can make it publicly available it will be hosted at zenodo
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Digital methods. Text editors and music player
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): The software to access the data is of common use
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Zenodo (no code) (in case of public disclosure)

³⁰ State the purpose of the data collection/generation.

9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Signature of EULA agreement for research (in case of public disclosure)
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	No, the recorded data only consists of scripted, invented and unstructured dialogues among the participants
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	yes
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Internal: Using VPN credentials, secure connections and servers access with ssh In case of publicly available through a EULA license signature

B3 - Making data interoperable

1	File format			
	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify): audio (wav or mp3) files
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	CTM format annotations for transcriptions and file metadata		

B4 - Increase data re-use

1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	EULA agreement for research
2	Data owner	TID
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	Need to check with our legal department and internal data processing policy
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): But depending on TID's internal privacy policy we are thinking to open access data for general research purposes
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	2 years after the end of the project

C - Personal Data

If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions

1	What types of personal data will you process?	Name and email of participants
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	Contact involved participants
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	Allowing right of withdrawal from the recordings and compliance national and European regulations
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	No or not aware of them
D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	Secure server with restricted access to TID employees involved in ELOQUENCE and EPG (TID department for server maintenance)
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	Manual backup is performed every 6 months. Data is encrypted in a volume using ecryptfs-utils in a ubuntu server. It uses a passphrase and aes cipher with 32 key bytes. The volume is mounted manually at server restart.
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	After processing and curation, publicly available data will be stored in zenodo repository: https://zenodo.org/communities/eloquenceai
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	Access to server for processing and storing data is restricted to TID employees. It needs a VPN access and secure shell connection. When server is shutdown, data is encrypted in a volume using ecryptfs-utils in a ubuntu server. It uses a passphrase and aes cipher with 32 key bytes. The volume is mounted manually at server restart.
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): personal data tokens randomly generated and only provided to participants <input type="checkbox"/> No
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	No

ii. CNR

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Data collection is included in the activities of Pilot 2, "Social context-aware language model detecting biases," and concerns information gathered from participants through Focus Group discussions and Questionnaires (online and paper-based). The collected data are in line with the activities of WP5 and will be used to evaluate the capacity to generate socially acceptable statements of an agent built on top of Eloquence technologies.
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	The activities aim to collect/generate the following data: personal data (e.g. gender and age), initial bias assessment, evaluation of conversation generated using the Eloquence tools
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	The specific format of data is under elaboration. Nevertheless, it is foreseen that the data will be collected from questionnaires completed by participants.
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
5	What is the origin of the data?	The data will be collected from participants involved in Pilot 2; however, this is still under discussion before being finalized.
6	What is the expected size of the data?	At the moment we do not know this information.

7	To whom might the data be useful?	Research groups in the fields of Human-machine interactions, human behaviour, and artificial intelligence. The Private sector that might be interested in solutions that can automate communication with customers.
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): The principles relating to the processing of personal data, as enshrined in the GDPR, will be carefully considered in all phases of the Pilot 2. Privacy preservation techniques will be applied to the collected data in order to guarantee anonymization. Further details will be defined in the continuation of the activities
B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	FAIR Principles are ensured by selecting a general-purpose open repository to allows the researchers involved in the project to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts.
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	The need and the definition of which type of metadata will be created is still under discussion before being finalized.
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	At present, we consider that there are no restrictions on data sharing.
3	How will the data be made accessible	Through an open repository enabling the CNR researchers to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. Zenodo might be a possible solution (https://zenodo.org/communities/eloquenceai)
4	Which repository will be used?	A possible solution might be Zenodo because, for each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citeable.
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Accessing data in Zenodo can be done in a few ways: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Locate datasets via Zenodo ElasticSearch feature that allows users to locate datasets. · Browse datasets via the Zenodo communities directory.
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the Zenodo repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it.
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	No.

11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	No.
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Zenodo users are granted access to the data via their user account and agree to share with the record owners their full name and email address.
B3 - Making data interoperable		
1	File format	
	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ Other (please specify):
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	(meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles. For certain terms, it refers to open, external vocabularies, e.g., license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE).
B4 - Increase data re-use		
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata and is referring to an Open Definition license, but within ELOQUENCE project we reserve the possibility to restrict the access in case of sensitive data.
2	Data owner	All data and metadata uploaded are traceable to a registered Zenodo user. Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	<p>Zenodo supports restricted access to data. There are three options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closed Access: Files may be deposited under closed access, which are protected against unauthorised access at all levels. • Embargoed Access: Users may deposit content under an embargo status and provide an end date for the embargo. The repository will restrict access to the data until the end of the embargo period; at which time, the content will become publicly available automatically. • Restricted Access: Users may deposit restricted files with the ability to share access with others if certain requirements are met. These files will not be made publicly available, and sharing will be made possible only by the approval of the depositor of the original file. <p>Given the flexibility of the repository, the decision of when making the data available can be taken during the continuation of the project activities.</p>
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	5 years after the conclusion of the project
C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		

1	What types of personal data will you process?	We currently plan to process the following personal data: gender, age, level of study, position, and interviews.
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	The personal data will be processed for conducting interviews necessary for research purposes.
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	The personal data are relevant to determining the participant's initial bias assessment and, consequently, to analysing the data produced.
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Ethical issues will be respected in sharing the data; no criticalities are currently evident.
D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	We believe that a possible solution to store the collected data is to use Zenodo repository.
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	<p>One of the main reasons for Zenodo adoption is because of the security it provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The data centres are located on CERN premises, and all physical access is restricted to a limited staff with appropriate training and who have been granted access in line with their professional duties. • The servers are managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers, meaning, e.g. remote access to our servers are restricted to Zenodo staff with appropriate training, and the operating system and installed applications are kept updated with latest security patches via the automatic configuration management system Puppet. • The CERN Security Team runs both host- and network-based intrusion detection systems and monitors the traffic flow, pattern, and contents into and out of CERN networks to detect attacks. All access to zenodo.org happens over HTTPS, except for static documentation pages, which are hosted on GitHub Pages. • Zenodo stores user passwords using strong cryptographic password hashing algorithms (currently PBKDF2+SHA512). Users' access tokens to GitHub and ORCID are stored encrypted and can only be decrypted with the application's secret key. • Zenodo also employs a suite of techniques to protect your session from being stolen by an attacker when a user is logged in and runs vulnerability scans against the application. Moreover, during the project. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information will be kept in locked filing cabinets and password-protected computers in a room with restricted access at the premises of the 5 partners participating in the pilot. • Back up will be kept in an external hard disc locked in another room. • Data transfers will be done through SFTPs
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Please, see point D.2.

4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	Please, see point D.2.
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No Zenodo has procedures for erasure and deletion of data. More specifically, it will always be possible to delete an unpublished record, while published records cannot be deleted except under special circumstances.
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	No

iii. BSC

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? ¹	We process the data collected by the other partners. The purpose is to run the pilots defined in WP5. We are also providing assistance to the different partners.
2	What types of data you will generate/collect? ²	Audio files and text files.
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect? ³	mp3/wav files / automatic transcriptions / intent and slot annotations / conversational data
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how? ⁴	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
5	What is the origin of the data? ⁵	Data origin has to be defined by the other partners that will use BSC infrastructure.
6	What is the expected size of the data? ⁶	N/A
7	To whom might the data be useful? ⁷	WP1 for metrics and benchmark, WP2 for grounding

		<i>LLMs, WPS for development of pilot number 1</i>
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data? ⁸	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Each partner utilizing the BSC infrastructure must independently define it, as BSC's role is limited to providing computational resources. Generated data at BSC will be synthetic and will not require any anonymization methods.

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	<i>Each partner utilizing the BSC infrastructure must independently define metadata that BSC will process, as BSC's role is limited to providing computational resources.</i> <i>Regarding the metadata generated at BSC: Speech Transcriptions. Synthetic conversational data.</i>
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline? ⁹	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): ctm format for transcriptions, xml format for synthetic data <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	N/A
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use? ¹⁰	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility ¹¹	<input type="checkbox"/> Public data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why ¹²	<i>The data is provided by other partners and may contain confidential information, thereby restricting the possibility of making our generated data publicly accessible.</i>
3	How will the data be made accessible ¹³	<i>Under EULA agreement for research purpose</i>
4	Which repository will be used? ¹⁴	<i>In case we can make it publicly available it will be hosted at zenodo</i>

5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Digital methods. Text editors and music player
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? ¹⁵	Zenodo (no code) (in case of public disclosure)
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Signature of EULA agreement for research (in case of public disclosure)
10	Is there a need for a data access committee? ¹⁶	No, our focus will be on synthetically generated data that does not contain any information from actual users.
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	yes
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Internal: Using VPN credentials, secure connections to access BSC storage servers In case of publicly available through an EULA license signature
B3 - Making data interoperable		
1	File format	
	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON
		Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ
		Other (please specify): TSV
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	CTM format annotations for transcriptions and file metadata
B4 - Increase data re-use		
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? ¹⁷	EULA agreement for research
2	Data owner ¹⁸	BSC

3	When will the data be made available for re-use? ¹⁹	Need to check with our legal department and internal data processing policy.
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? ²⁰	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): Depends on the other partner's internal policies.
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable? ²¹	End of the project

C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		
1	What types of personal data will you process? ²²	Each partner utilizing the BSC infrastructure must independently define it, as BSC's role is limited to providing computational resources.
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data? ²³	Each partner utilizing the BSC infrastructure must independently define it, as BSC's role is limited to providing computational resources.
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	Allowing right of withdrawal from the recordings and compliance national and European regulations.
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR? ²⁴	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data? ²⁵	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	No

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	Secure server with restricted access to BSC employees involved in ELOQUENCE and the different partners from ELOQUENCE that require BSC's computational resources.
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data) ²⁶	TBC with internal security department
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	TBC with internal security department
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	TBC with internal security department
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): TBC with internal security department <input type="checkbox"/> No

E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? ²⁷	TBC

iv. FBK

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	We are not collecting or generating any data. We will use publicly available data.
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	We are not collecting or generating any data. We will use publicly available data.
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	We are not collecting or generating any data. We will use publicly available data.
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): we will use public data containing speech and text. We will employ use case data.
5	What is the origin of the data?	Different sources. Data are open or usable for research
6	What is the expected size of the data?	GB (max 1-2 TB)
7	To whom might the data be useful?	We are not going to collect data, the data that we will use are publicly available
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	We will not generate data and metadata
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): I think no but I am not sure
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	Please Specify
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No we are not generating data
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data We do not generate data, we use public data or data generated by other partners.
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	Please Specify
3	How will the data be made accessible	Please Specify
4	Which repository will be used?	Please Specify
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Please Specify
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):

8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Please Specify
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Please Specify
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	Please Specify
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	Please Specify
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Not necessary
B3 - Making data interoperable		
1	File format Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	Please Specify
B4 - Increase data re-use		
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	No data generated
2	Data owner	No data generated
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	No data generated
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): No data generated
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	No data generated
C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		
1	What types of personal data will you process?	We will process voices (speech data)
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	To perform speech recognition
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	We only process to transcribe what has been said, the dataset owner has the right to process and release the data
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No Most likely not
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No we process speech data collected by other entities and made available publicly

6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No <i>No, The use case data may not be sharable outside the consortium but we are not owners.</i>
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Not at the moment</i>

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	Servers in FBK (or HPC providers used by FBK)
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	<i>None, data are public, not ours. For pilot's data we will implement what is requested</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	No
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<i>User name and password</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No <i>No but I guess we do not need.</i>
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	No

v. UNS

General Information	
Partner Name	UNS
Corresponding person (email)	Milan Sečujski (secujski@uns.ac.rs)
Name of the dataset	UNS Call Centre Conversation Dataset

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<i>Use as training data in the development of a virtual agent aimed at supporting the work of medical practitioners in call centres.</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	<i>Text & audio data (staged recordings).</i>
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	<i>json (text), wav (audio).</i>
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
5	What is the origin of the data?	<i>Audio data include staged recordings of human dialogues following predefined topics and loosely predefined question/answer sequences. The public section of the dataset includes manual transcriptions of the recordings, edited principally for clarity, and annotated according to a predefined label schema, while audio recordings will not be made available to the general public.</i>
6	What is the expected size of the data?	<i>150 dialogues</i>

7	To whom might the data be useful?	The data will be useful to researches working on the development of virtual agents at the project ELOQUENCE, but it may also be useful to any research entity working in natural language processing and development of dialogue systems.
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Dialogues do not contain personal data, and data about the participants will be omitted from the metadata in the case of the public section of the dataset.

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	We will organize textual data (edited and annotated transcriptions) so that they will be discoverable with metadata. No personal data will be disclosed to any third-party (i.e. non-consortium entities) unless there is an explicit authorization to do so by the interested individual or there is a contractual obligation to be fulfilled.
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Among a number of existing standards, TEI will be used to describe edited and annotated transcriptions. OLAC or IMDI will be used for audio recordings, but not with the purpose of making the data discoverable. <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	Not applicable
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data Only the textual part of the dataset (edited and annotated dialogue transcriptions) will be made public, while audio data will be shared only between Project partners. By default, for all the datasets produced within UNS experiments, UNS will be the sole owner of the data. Accessibility will be defined in accordance to the UNS Data protection policy and Policy for Research infrastructure.
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	Annotated textual data will be shared with open research community, while audio data will be shared only between Project partners
3	How will the data be made accessible	In accordance to the UNS Data protection policy and Policy for Research infrastructure, the public section of the dataset will be shared using a standard data-sharing platform.
4	Which repository will be used?	The platform for sharing the dataset will be one of the standard platforms for sharing research outputs, selected in accordance with the UNS Data protection policy and Policy for Research infrastructure.
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Data will be available without specific software.
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	All data and associated data will be deposited on secure UNS servers, and the public section of the data (edited and annotated transcriptions) will also be shared through a dedicated platform.
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Access to the public section of the dataset will be provided through a standard data-sharing platform, while access to the audio recordings will be provided to

		<i>Project partners through credentials enabling them to access data deposited on UNS servers.</i>
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	<i>No, since no personal data is included in either recordings or transcriptions.</i>
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	<i>An appropriate machine readable license will be provided to define conditions for access.</i>
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	<i>As regards the public section of the corpus, accessibility, including ascertaining the identity of the person accessing the data, will be defined in accordance to the rules of the data sharing platform, so as to adhere to UNS Data protection policy and Policy for Research infrastructure.</i>

B3 - Making data interoperable

File format				
1	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify): wav audio files
	2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	<i>TEI will be used to describe edited and annotated transcriptions. OLAC or IMDI will be used for audio recordings.</i>	

B4 - Increase data re-use

1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	<i>Data re-use will be defined in accordance with UNS Policy for Research infrastructure.</i>
2	Data owner	<i>For all the datasets produced within UNS experiments, UNS will be the sole owner of the data.</i>
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	<i>Edited dialogue transcriptions will be available for re-use along with the publication of main results.</i>
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	<i>As part of exploitation activities, UNS intends to integrate the ELOQUENCE UNS datasets to the existing Research infrastructure, with no time limitation.</i>

C - Personal Data

If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions

1	What types of personal data will you process?	<i>No personal data will be processed.</i>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	-
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	-
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	-

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	All data and associated data will be deposited on secure UNS servers, and the public section of the data (edited and annotated transcriptions) will also be shared through a dedicated platform, in accordance to the UNS Data protection policy and Policy for Research infrastructure.
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	UNS data servers support distributed network storage with RAID 1+1 protection.
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Yes
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	Access to the audio recordings (the non-public section of the dataset) will be provided to Project partners only, through credentials enabling them to access data deposited on UNS servers.
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	No

vi. EUI

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	EUI does not collect or process personal data of human subjects in ELOQUENCE, as it does not conduct empirical work. For its tasks in the project the EUI needs to rely on email addresses (and other contact info) of project participants
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	Email addresses and in some cases other contact information such as a phone number
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	doc, xlsx
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
5	What is the origin of the data?	The individuals concerned
6	What is the expected size of the data?	Small, less than 1 MB total

7	To whom might the data be useful?	For the leader and members of WP6, enabling communication between project partners and members of the ELOQUENCE Community of Experts. In light of this, there is no need to provide answers under the other sections.		
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):		
B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data				
B1 - Making data Findable				
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
2	What metadata will be created?	Please Specify		
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):		
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	Please Specify		
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
B2 - Making data openly accessible				
1	Accessibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data		
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	Please Specify		
3	How will the data be made accessible	Please Specify		
4	Which repository will be used?	Please Specify		
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Please Specify		
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):		
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Please Specify		
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Please Specify		
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	Please Specify		
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	Please Specify		
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Please Specify		
B3 - Making data interoperable				
1	File format			
	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM	Other (please specify):

	<input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	<input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	<input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	Please Specify	
B4 - Increase data re-use			
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	Please Specify	
2	Data owner	Please Specify	
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	Please Specify	
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):	
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	Please Specify	
C - Personal Data			
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions			
1	What types of personal data will you process?	Please Specify	
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	Please Specify	
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	Please Specify	
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No	
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No	
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No	
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No	
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Please Specify	
D- Data Security			
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	Please Specify	
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	Please Specify	
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Please Specify	

4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	Please Specify
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	Please Specify

ii. BUT

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Primary purpose is to synthesize factually grounded evaluation data for LLM-based dialogue system
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	We will generate textual data based on public sources and pre-trained LLMs
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	structured txt
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): We will re-use publicly available structured data, such as those provided by Linguistic Data Consortium and similar, we might re-use textual data obtained from sources under the public domain (or compatible) licenses
5	What is the origin of the data?	Synthesis from public LLMs and public textual sources
6	What is the expected size of the data?	Size of synthesized data is expected to be less than 1GB
7	To whom might the data be useful?	For the R&D in dialogue system design
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Since the data is synthesized, we do not consider anonymization. We will apply data aggregation and minimization to reduce redundancy if required.
B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	Language, source of grounding data, LLMs used for synthesis
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): We will use the "Data Cards" https://sites.research.google/datacardsplaybook/
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		

1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data			
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	NA			
3	How will the data be made accessible	online			
4	Which repository will be used?	Project website, Hugging face datasets			
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Web browser to download, otherwise any tool that can process structured text data.			
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):			
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Project website, public github			
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Access gateway (eg. Huggingface ecosystem already has such mechanism)			
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	No			
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	Not applicable, public data			
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Not applicable, public data			
B3 - Making data interoperable					
1	File format	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	At present, we do not consider any specific data and metadata vocabularies to describe the data. Should the nature of the created data allow it, we will attempt to define common vocabulary for pre-defined values for harmonising the descriptions of the datapoints.			
B4 - Increase data re-use					
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0, or a license compatible with the use of a specific pre-trained LLM model, if it is more restrictive.			
2	Data owner	Brno University of Technology			
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	along with the publication of the main results			

4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	<i>as long as they bring relevant scientific or practical benefit (i.e. there is no time-limit on re-use)</i>
C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		
1	What types of personal data will you process?	<i>NONE</i>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	<i>Not applicable</i>
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	<i>Not applicable</i>
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Not applicable</i>
D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	<i>Open repository server, such as Zenodo or Hugging face</i>
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	<i>Once the data are generated, they will be stored on public repositories that implement their own security provisions. Data will be also stored on Brno University of Technology servers that are protected against disk failures and are regularly backed up.</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	<i>Data will be stored in respected public repositories implementing the required preservation standards.</i>
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<i>Data will be public, we do not restrict access.</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	<i>We follow the procedures of Brno University of Technology for long-term data storage.</i>

iii. INO

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<i>The purpose is to facilitate communication activities on the website, contact form, and newsletter.</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	<i>Text, images, numbers</i>
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	<i>.pdf; .jpg</i>
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
5	What is the origin of the data?	<i>The data originates from the contact form and newsletter subscription option on the eloquenceai.eu website.</i>
6	What is the expected size of the data?	<i>50mb</i>
7	To whom might the data be useful?	<i>The data may be useful to Eloquence project partners, particularly the WP7 communications lead, for communicating relevant information to the private sector, researchers, citizens, and all relevant stakeholders.</i>
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	<i>n/a</i>
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	<i>n/a</i>
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<i>x Confidential data</i>
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	<i>If certain datasets cannot be shared or need to be shared under restrictions, it's because we solely collect email addresses, which do not require sharing.</i>
3	How will the data be made accessible	<i>n/a</i>
4	Which repository will be used?	<i>Teams and ELOQUENCE website</i>
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	<i>Access to the data is facilitated through Brevo for newsletter sign-ups and via email, specifically through the contact form redirection to info@eloquenceai.eu.</i>
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	<i>The data and associated materials will be deposited in the Brevo dashboard for newsletter signups.</i>
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	<i>Access will be limited to InoSens team members involved in the project and to ELOQUENCE project partners upon request.</i>
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	<i>n/a</i>
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	<i>n/a</i>
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	<i>n/a</i>

B3 - Making data interoperable	
1	File format Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ Other (please specify):
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow? <i>n/a</i>
B4 - Increase data re-use	
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? <i>n/a</i>
2	Data owner <i>InoSens (WP7 lead)</i>
3	When will the data be made available for re-use? <i>n/a</i>
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable? <i>n/a</i>
C - Personal Data	
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions	
1	What types of personal data will you process? <i>Email address</i>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data? <i>It's primarily for contacting relevant stakeholders to respond to their inquiries submitted through the contact form. Additionally, we utilize it to communicate pertinent project information through our newsletter.</i>
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project? <i>Our collection of personal data is confined to email addresses obtained through the contact and newsletter forms, with prior consent obtained before sending. This information is necessary for communicating with and responding to inquiries.</i>
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? <i>n/a</i>
D- Data Security	
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored? <i>AdminProject, InoSens internal servers</i>
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data) <i>All data will be stored on AdminProject. All data is also safely stored on InoSens internal servers, access made available only to people working on the project.</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation? <i>Yes</i>

4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<i>InoSens has put in place internal protocols (technical security protocols, also, only personnel working on the project have access to this data) for storing project partners information.</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	No

iv. TL

General Information	
Partner Name	Transformation Lighthouse
Corresponding person (email)	martin@transformation-lighthouse.com
Name of the dataset	/

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<i>In our task of business sustainability, we were mostly in research mode collecting publicly available data for the business market report. In the future we will be in contact with potential clients conducting primary research. All the data gathered will serve as a part of understanding the market needs and further help the development of the LLM research teams.</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	Business market report. Later conversational data about customer understanding and usage of the technology. Their personal and business information...
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	<i>Ideally full transcriptions of conversations would be available but mostly we see mostly notes about the conversations to be collected.</i>
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
5	What is the origin of the data?	<i>Public available data and interview generated data.</i>
6	What is the expected size of the data?	<i>100 – 500 interviews conducted <10 gb</i>
7	To whom might the data be useful?	<i>To development team, our team and the project viability for market entry.</i>
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	General survey metadata
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	<i>The metadata depend on the project and feedback received.</i>
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		

1	Accessibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Public data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	<i>Most of the data received will not be shared but only collected for the purpose of internal decision making.</i>
3	How will the data be made accessible	<i>It will not be accessible by anyone outside the research teams and TL. The results will be published based on the data.</i>
4	Which repository will be used?	<i>Local repository on a locked device.</i>
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	<i>None</i>
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	<i>Stored locally on the business device and in hard copies based on the notes taken during the process.</i>
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	<i>All data on the business devices is accessible only by physical access and needed security login to access the device.</i>
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	<i>No</i>
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	<i>No</i>
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	<i>The identity of the person is Martin Jarc inside the TL team. Personal password alone no other teammate will have the access.</i>

B3 - Making data interoperable

1	File format	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML			
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	<i>No specific methodologies.</i>		

B4 - Increase data re-use

1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	<i>It will not be used.</i>
2	Data owner	<i>TL</i>
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	<i>It will not be.</i>
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): <i>The data will not be used further otherwise before the interviews the participants should sign a document agreeing to their data to be used. This limits the interview quality and sincerity.</i>
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	<i>For 3 years after the end of the project</i>

C - Personal Data

If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions

1	What types of personal data will you process?	<i>Personal name, position, company details, email and job position.</i>
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2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	<i>In order to rank and map the market. In order to ensure possible reach out in later stages of the project.</i>
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	<i>We are only taking limited personal data of those who are willing to share them. It will help us create leads and in the end ensure business sustainability.</i>
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	/

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	<i>Business computer of TL data officer and in backup HD.</i>
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	<i>There are backups done regularly by our data protection officer.</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	<i>No</i>
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<i>The business computer of TL' data officer is on a safe location at all times and locked with a password. No encryption on the files will be done.</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): For personal data collected at our event the procedure is deletion of all personal data collected after 5 years or in case of personal request sooner.: <input type="checkbox"/> No

E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	<i>Not really. All our personal data collected follows our privacy policy on our website and on all application forms we collect.</i>

v. GX

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<i>Surveys under WP6 (T6.3), potential webinars for dissemination purposes, E-mails for communication etc.</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	<i>We will collect data from survey responses, partners and stakeholders</i>

3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	MS office, google forms and excel forms
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
5	What is the origin of the data?	E-mails, and some names
6	What is the expected size of the data?	We don't know yet
7	To whom might the data be useful?	Consortium
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): as opposed to the respondents' contact details.
B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	Graphs and statistical analysis, but without using identifying elements of participants
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	N/A
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	Share with organisations in consortium and EC, personal contacts of participants in survey, potential webinars and roundtable discussions.
3	How will the data be made accessible	Public results will be shared according to EU laws and IP management regulations. Confidential data from participants will not be shared. Internal database in company (for participants from GX) will be used to collect confidential data from participants.
4	Which repository will be used?	N/A
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Company credentials
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Project outcomes as stated above will be stored and deposited in line with EC regulations and compliance. Participants personal data will not be stored anywhere aside company's private database
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	EU legislation on IP Management
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	N/A
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	N/A
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	N/A
B3 - Making data interoperable		
1	File format	

Spreadsheet: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JPG <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
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2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	<i>Scientific publications, EC reports etc</i>
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B4 - Increase data re-use

1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	In accordance to EC legislation and IP management regulations
2	Data owner	In accordance to EC legislation and IP management regulations
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	During and after the project
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): the data will be visible to the consortium and the project officer during the implementation of project and for mandate amount of time after the completion of the project.
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	3 years

C - Personal Data

If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions

1	What types of personal data will you process?	<i>Consortium personal data, personal data and contact details from stakeholders etc</i>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	<i>Conduct Surveys (T6.3), potential participation in roundtables and webinars etc</i>
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	<i>Surveys validation, Newsletter and other events sharing (contact details: name, surname, email address, phone number, position in organisation, organisation, city, country, address of organisation)</i>
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): between consortium of project and the EU officer and EC <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Handling of data will be done in accordance and compliance to EC legislation on IP management and the Data management plan of the project</i>

D- Data Security

1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	GrantXpert is working with Microsoft 365. All Projects use as storage space, SharePoint provided by Microsoft 365.
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2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	GrantXpert has a subscription for each employee on VEEAM 365 BACKUP, which allow us to recover any data loss. Also, GX pays for service from Cyprus Telecommunication Authority (CYTA) for SDWAN service with Advanced Security, Remote VPN, Security and Encrypted data
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	GX utilises all available features of Microsoft 365.
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	Only Specific Employees have access to Project's Folder in SharePoint. No other user either from organization or outside the organization has access. MFA is enabled to all GX Employees to prevent unauthorised access to data.
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	No

vi. OM

General Information	
Partner Name	Omilia
Corresponding person (email)	tstafylakis@omilia.com
Name of the dataset	—

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Gather results and feedback for further fine-tuning and improving the LLMs. Demonstrate the effectiveness and capabilities of the developed retrieval augmented generation
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	Text and numeric
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	txt, (structured) json, csv, xlsx
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes: Given data and information are provided by the project partners these will be utilized for retrieval augmented generation
5	What is the origin of the data?	Project partners
6	What is the expected size of the data?	Currently unspecified since generation is still ongoing
7	To whom might the data be useful?	To the rest of the project participants either for evaluation/assessment reasons or for refining the LLMs under consideration
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	—

3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): For the use cases that we are going to be working on, no specific metadata standards apply		
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	At least initially, no metadata will be created-devised		
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No: Apart from the respective formal name and description no additional search-tailored information will be included		
B2 - Making data openly accessible				
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confidential data, depending on the case and on the common decision of the involved members and partners		
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	—		
3	How will the data be made accessible	Via open access repositories and according to the consortiums guidelines		
4	Which repository will be used?	Project's website, git and cloud spaces		
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Basic file reading/accessing methods		
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): As mentioned, straightforward file reading techniques are sufficient		
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	In the landing pages of the repositories mentioned previously		
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	If such a requirement surfaces then it will be addressed uniformly across the project based on what will be decided		
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	No		
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	No		
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	If applicable, via login credentials and potentially via a two-factor authorization approach		
B3 - Making data interoperable				
1	File format Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	—		
B4 - Increase data re-use				
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	By using a version of the suite of Creative Commons (CC) copyright licences		
2	Data owner	The respective creator as well as Eloquence		
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	At the latest, by the end of the project		
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):		

5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	<i>Indefinitely as long as they remain relevant</i>
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C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		
1	What types of personal data will you process?	<i>No personal data will be processed</i>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	—
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	—
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	—

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	<i>Final versions of certain datasets are going to be stored in open access repositories whereas all the rest are going to be stored in Omilia's cloud infrastructure</i>
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	<i>All those specified by the information security and data protection frameworks detailed in section E.1</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	<i>All those specified by the information security and data protection frameworks detailed in section E.1</i>
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<i>All those specified by the information security and data protection frameworks detailed in section E.1</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? ³¹	<i>Omilia complies with all the major Information Security and Data Protection Global, Regional and State regulatory frameworks and standards, including ISO/IEC 27001, Cyber Essentials, AICPA SOC, GDPR</i>

³¹ Indicate if you must adhere to other policies and procedures for data management.

vii. SYN

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? ¹	Definition of additional information and prompt databases, adapting LLMs to complex conversational data in the context of WP2
2	What types of data you will generate/collect? ²	Text (Audio transcription dialogues and text dialogues).
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect? ³	json, txt, xlsx
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how? ⁴	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Open datasets are evaluated in the context of WP1
5	What is the origin of the data? ⁵	Open repositories
6	What is the expected size of the data? ⁶	Variable, TBD
7	To whom might the data be useful? ⁷	Research groups mainly
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data? ⁸	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	<i>Not decided yet</i>
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline? ⁹	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	<i>Not decided yet</i>
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use? ¹⁰	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility ¹¹	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why? ¹²	<i>Confidential data may only be produced during project pilot activities</i>
3	How will the data be made accessible? ¹³	<i>If any new dataset would be created as a combination of already existing, data will be deposited in a repository</i>
4	Which repository will be used? ¹⁴	<i>Not decided yet</i>
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Python libraries
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): (if any new dataset would be created)
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? ¹⁵	<i>Local drive server.</i>
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	<i>N/A</i>
10	Is there a need for a data access committee? ¹⁶	<i>No</i>
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	<i>If any new dataset would be created, data will be accompanied with a machine readable license</i>
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	<i>Data are stored on encrypted disks, computer accounts are password protected, according to the SYN password policy, and applies communication security measures according to the Data Security Plan.</i>

B3 - Making data interoperable		
1	File format Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON
	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	<i>Not decided yet.</i>
B4 - Increase data re-use		
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? ¹⁷	<i>Not decided yet.</i>
2	Data owner ¹⁸	<i>To be completed later</i>
3	When will the data be made available for re-use? ¹⁹	<i>Open datasets are already available</i>
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? ²⁰	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable? ²¹	<i>6 months after the end of the project</i>

C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		
1	What types of personal data will you process? ²²	<i>The audio recording dialogues and the text dialogues may contain human names and/or addresses</i>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data? ²³	<i>For validation of developed AI models during pilots</i>
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	<i>They will be used only to ensure the operation of AI models during pilots</i>
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR? ²⁴	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

5	Will you process previously collected personal data? ²⁵	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No Data would be shared only with project partners
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	No

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	<i>Privately managed storage</i>
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data) ²⁶	<i>SYN applies a Data Security Plan, compliant to ISO/IEC 27001:2017. Data are stored on encrypted disks, computer accounts are password protected, according to the SYN password policy, and applies communication security measures according to the Data Security Plan.</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	<i>ISO27001 certified infrastructure</i>
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<i>Data are stored on encrypted disks, computer accounts are password protected, according to the SYN password policy, and applies communication security measures according to the Data Security Plan.</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? ²⁷	No

viii. IDIAP

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<i>Creating the largest dataset with standardized action annotations for task-oriented dialogs, specifically to develop a system which can generate action-driven soft contrastive embeddings for automatic dialog flow extraction.</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	<i>Data is neither generated, not collected. We only identify and put together existing datasets available in repositories. All the data is textual data with some structure such as json.</i>
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	<i>All data is textual data, e.g. stored to be machine readable - json format – with per-utterance annotations.</i> <i>The JSON structure has two main parts: a "stats" header and a "dialogs" body. The "stats" field provides statistics about the labels and domains in the dataset. The "dialogs" field contains dialog IDs, each linked to a list of annotated utterance objects. Each utterance object includes its speaker, text, domains, and associated labels for dialog acts, slots, and intents. Dialog act labels contain the original labels ("original_acts") as well as their</i>

		standardized values ("acts") and parent values ("main_acts").
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): This data will be used for the work on generating embeddings (representations of utterances) for task oriented dialogs
5	What is the origin of the data?	The data is public, the collection is described in 20 different 20 different papers, and can be accessed from corresponding repositories provided by authors.
6	What is the expected size of the data?	All is text data. The data is associated with the necessary annotations, manually standardizing domain names and dialog act labels across datasets. For our use in Eloquence, we unified all datasets under a consistent format, incorporating per-turn dialog act and slot annotations. The resulting unified TOD dataset comprises 3.4 million utterances annotated with 18 standardized dialog acts, 524 unique slot labels, 205 and 3,982 unique action labels (dialog act + slots) 206 spanning across 52 different domains.
7	To whom might the data be useful?	The plan is to use this large and unique set of data for dialogue modelling, specifically for dialog flow analysis.
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): We do not need to apply anything like this. Data is anonymized, and not possible for human or machine to uncover any identity, etc.
B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	There is no need for metadata, as we use json format which contains all necessary information.
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Metadata is used in the field of dialogue modelling. <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	N/A
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Data is searchable as this is text data.
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	All data as part of this set of 20 datasets can be shared – we only create an index, combine the data to follow an unified format, and let user to deploy data themselves (including downloading automatically data from original sources). We are therefore not data owners.
3	How will the data be made accessible	Data is accessible also now, only the set of scripts was created to let everyone to download the data in one step (20 datasets in total).
4	Which repository will be used?	Code will be released through github.com
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Python scripts will be released.
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): Not understand question.
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Released as technical paper, together with github repository.
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	No restriction. The code to automaticall download the data will be done under We will use MIT license for our code. To make it more clear: However, to prevent potential license incompatibilities among the various task-oriented dialogue (TOD) datasets we have utilized, we will not release our unified TOD dataset directly. Instead, we will provide a script

		that can generate the unified dataset introduced in this paper. This approach allows users to select the specific TOD datasets they wish to include, ensuring compliance with individual dataset licenses.
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	No
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	Yes
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	To access the scripts for data download, all will be done through <i>github</i> .
B3 - Making data interoperable		
1	File format	
	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON
		Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	N/A
B4 - Increase data re-use		
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	MIT license
2	Data owner	Data is owned by the data producers (different for each of 20 datasets).
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	Our scripts was automatically accessing and downloading data will be released after the paper is accepted on the conference.
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	Depending on the data owners (20 datasets). This is not under our control.
C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		
1	What types of personal data will you process?	No personal data.
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	N/A
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	N/A
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	We acknowledge that gender bias present in the original data could be partially encoded in the embeddings. This may manifest as assumptions about the agent's gender, such as the agent being male or

		<i>female. We advise users to be aware of this potential bias and encourage further research to mitigate such issues. Continuous efforts to audit and address biases in data and models are essential to ensure fair and equitable AI systems.</i>
D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	<i>Github.com</i>
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	<i>Github takes care of this.</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	<i>Yes</i>
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<i>Data will be publically available.</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): We can delete the github repo if required. <input type="checkbox"/> No
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	<i>We follow requirements for data processing and management based on Swiss legislative.</i>

ix. BUL

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<i>Evaluation of the LLM across a range of domains (Bias, conversational ability, understanding, truthfulness, multilinguality, multimodality, as well as potential for fine-tuning. WP1.1-1.5</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	<i>Text data – both structured and unstructured. Covering the above domains</i>
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	<i>Collected data will be .txt, .json, .csv, .arrow Processed data will likely be .json, with compression</i>
4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes: <i>Existing open-source datasets will be used and processed to improve overall quality and suitability</i>
5	What is the origin of the data?	<i>HuggingFace and LLM generated data with human validation, recording using smart room in Telefonica (This collection will be controlled and processed by Telefonica).. Origins of open source data being used may vary.</i>
6	What is the expected size of the data?	<i><50GB expected</i>
7	To whom might the data be useful?	<i>Research groups, academia, industries related to the conversational agents, private groups wishing to evaluate LLMs</i>
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes: Aggregation: data will be fused across multiple sources Minimisation: Data will be evaluated for quality, and poor-quality data will be removed Anonymisation: Likely to be no personal data within, but anonymisation will be applied if this occurs.

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data									
B1 - Making data Findable									
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No								
2	What metadata will be created? Sources of data, and contextual data that is task dependent (i.e. for conversation – speaker ID)								
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): No standards have yet been established								
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how <i>To be determined following further research. However, metadata will likely include source URL's to aid in making data findable</i>								
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No – Data sources and keywords will be used when dataset is made public								
B2 - Making data openly accessible									
1	Accessibility <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data								
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why <i>N/A</i>								
3	How will the data be made accessible <i>Deposition into a repository</i>								
4	Which repository will be used? <i>HuggingFace, GitHub, Open source dataset repository such as IEEE Open</i>								
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? <i>Open-source download, no specialist tools required</i>								
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No								
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):								
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? <i>HuggingFace – Data and metadata GitHub – Documentation and code</i>								
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided? <i>N/A</i>								
10	Is there a need for a data access committee? <i>No – No controlled data will be utilised</i>								
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)? <i>Open-source data, with instructions for use</i>								
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained? <i>It will not be</i>								
B3 - Making data interoperable									
1	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="4" style="text-align: center;">File format</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="width: 25%; vertical-align: top;"> Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML </td> <td style="width: 25%; vertical-align: top;"> Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON </td> <td style="width: 25%; vertical-align: top;"> Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ </td> <td style="width: 25%; vertical-align: top;"> Other (please specify): .zip .arrow </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	File format				Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify): .zip .arrow
File format									
Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify): .zip .arrow						
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow? <i>HuggingFace standards</i>								
B4 - Increase data re-use									
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? <i>CC-BY-4.0</i>								
2	Data owner <i>Open-access datasets to be used, if the dataset is generated by BUL – the owner is BUL</i>								

3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	At the end of project
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	5 years after the conclusion of the project
C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		
1	What types of personal data will you process?	N/A
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	N/A
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	N/A
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No Data will be uploaded to a repository for public use
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	N/A
D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	Cloud storage solutions: Microsoft SharePoint
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	Microsoft data security procedures in place
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	It will be
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	2 factor authentication Sharing only with ELOQUENCE partners
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	No

x. UESSEX

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	We will use publicly available datasets for building multi-lingual and multi-modal models for conversational system
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	We will use publicly available text and audio datasets.
3	What formats of data you will generate/collect?	Datasets used will be in text and audio format.

4	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): We will use datasets selected in WP1
5	What is the origin of the data?	Different originals based on the source.
6	What is the expected size of the data?	Text data size in Billions of texts and audio in hundreds of hours depending on dataset selected in WP1
7	To whom might the data be useful?	For all partners in the project and other research community.
8	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	NA, not meta data will be created
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Yes, however, it is not clear at this moment what standard will be used <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	Please Specify
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	NA, all public datasets will be used.
3	How will the data be made accessible	Yes, all public datasets will be used.
4	Which repository will be used?	All public datasets will be used, which used different repository. Link to repository will be provided on the code GitHub/GitLab pages.
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Python
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	We will release all codes to reproduce results on GitHub/GitLab pages.
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	We will follow the original datasets restriction.
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	NA, due to use of public datasets.
11	Are there well described conditions for access (e.g. a machine readable license, etc.)?	NA, due to use of public datasets.
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	NA, due to use of public datasets.
B3 - Making data interoperable		
1	File format	

	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify): We will use the data in the same format, as provided from WP1
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	NA, use the same standard as provide by the original dataset		
B4 - Increase data re-use				
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	NA, due to use of public datasets same re-use conditions will be followed.		
2	Data owner	original datasets owners.		
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	Datasets used are already publicly available.		
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): Dataset need to follow the same condition as original datasets.		
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	As long as it is made available by the original owner		
C - Personal Data				
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions				
1	What types of personal data will you process?	No personal data processing.		
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	NA		
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	NA		
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): We will process data based on the algorithmic requirement <input type="checkbox"/> No		
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): We will share the processing code of the data for the reproducibility <input type="checkbox"/> No		
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		
8	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Please Specify: NA		
D- Data Security				
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	WP1 dataset are publicly available at different sources		
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	NA, since these datasets are publicly available		
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	NA, since these datasets are publicly available		
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	NA, since these datasets are publicly available		
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): NA, since these datasets are publicly available <input type="checkbox"/> No		
E - Other Issues				

1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	<i>NA, datasets used publicly available</i>
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